

USE OF ICT IN D.T.ED.COLLEGES FOR ACTION RESEARCH

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Introduction:-

Teaching-learning process is going to change day to day because the need of our society is changing and as per requirement of our society, competitive world teaching learning process is mostly depends on technology. In past days teacher center education in classroom but these days teacher is became a facilitator and he providing verity of facilities to student which helpful to students to learns better. Educationalists also approved ICT as a best teaching resources and scientific method for teaching and useful for all subjects. In these days ICT is a blessing for education it gives verity of resources to teachers, students and every learner who uses ICT as teaching tool .ICT also useful in distance education with the help of ICT student got maximum information in minimum time. The ICT is very useful in all areas of human life. In all stages of education we need better tool who gives best result and research help to guide teacher, student and educational process to choose appropriate tool who gives quality education. Teacher education always prepare teacher for tomorrow with the help of research. D.T.Ed.college students learn ICT and Action research as a separate subject if they collaborate there knowledge of this two subject they save their time and learn to live with global thinking and update knowledge.

Information communication technology is also calling ICT as short form and that each word has separate meaning as follows.

Information:-

Information about someone or something consists of facts about them.

Collins cobuild advanced dictionary of English ©

Harper Collins publishers 2009

Communication:-

The exchange of meanings between individuals through a common system of symbols.

The new encyclopedia Britannica, volume -3

Technology: - The application of scientific knowledge to the practical aims of human life.

The new encyclopedia Britannica, volume -11

Collective meaning of these three words in education ICT and the Concept of ICT is “Its combination of three words Information, communication and technology. It includes anything that will store, strive, manipulate, transmit, or receive information electronically in digital forms.”

Action Research:-

Systematic enquiry designed to yield practical result capable of improving a specific aspects of practice and made public to enable scrutiny and testing.

Small scale intervention in the functioning of the real world and a close examination of effects of such intervention.

Cohen and Manion 1980

The discoveries and inventions in science and technology improved the speed of communication of exact information all this consist ICT. In 21st century ICT provide information in large scale and the society also becoming a knowledge society. Educational research provides information to develop educational policy and new teaching techniques, strategy to boost knowledge. If researchers get help of technology he got accurate result and also scientific information also.

Benefits of using ICT in action research:-

- ❖ ICT encourage performance based learning and researching.
- ❖ Researcher also uses various university websites to getting research review with the help of ICT.
- ❖ ICT Provide accurate and latest information to researcher which is more helpful for completing research.

- ❖ ICT assure students to 24/7 learning.
- ❖ Mobile learning, video conferencing learning

These facilities encourage student to learn better and it also economical. Student gets more information through internet and they learn through online resources. Example: library, elaborator, journals, e-publications, various websites, Wikipedia, Encyclopedia etc. This kind of resources available for students to learn individually and student learn with their own speed.

Objectives of research:-

- 1) To study the resources of ICT used by D.T.Ed.second year students.
- 2) To study difficulties of students using ICT for research purpose.

Assumption:-

- 1) Use of ICT is useful for action research.
- 2) Students of D.T.Ed. Second year use ICT for action research.

Scope and limitations of Research:-

- 1) Researcher conducted study on D.T.Ed. Second year students in Renuka adhyapak vidlaya, Renapur.
- 2) Research conducted on D.T.Ed.English medium students studied in academic year 2011-2012.

Sample of Research:-

Researcher chooses 40 students of D.T.Ed. Second year english medium by purposive sampling method to analyzing this data researcher used percentage as statistical parameter.

Research Methodology and Tool of data collection:-

Researcher conducted this research using survey method to study how students use ICT for stapes of action research like research review, data collection, analysis of data and report writing. Researcher use questioner as a tool for data collection.

Analysis of Data: Analysis of data researcher use percentage as statistical parameter. The analysis is as follows.

Table No.1

Students know about the concept of ICT

Sr. No.	Details	No. of students	Percentage
1	Yes	30	75%
2	No	10	25%
	Total	40	100%

Table No.1 shows that 75% students know the concept of ICT and 25% students don't define correctly what ICT is.

Table No.2

Students who use ICT in Research

Sr. No.	Details	No. of students	Percentage
1	Yes	11	27.50%
2	No	29	72.50%
	Total	40	100%

Table No.2 shows that 27.50% students use ICT in Research and 72.50% students are not using ICT in Research.

Table No.3

Students who use Internet for research review

Sr. No.	Details	No. of students	Percentage
1	Yes	08	20.00%
2	No	32	80.00%
	Total	40	100%

Table No.3 shows that 20.00% students use Internet for research review and 80.00% students are not using internet for research review.

Table No.4

Use of ICT is applicable in research

Sr. No.	Details	No. of students	Percentage
1	Yes	25	62.50%
2	No	15	37.50%
	Total	40	100%

Table No.4 shows that 62.50% students opinion is ICT is applicable in research and 37.50% students opinion is that ICT is not applicable in research.

Table No.5

Difficulties in using ICT as Resources

Sr. No.	Details	No. of students	Percentage
1	Un availability of Infrastructure	20	25%
2	Absence of Experts	06	15%
3	Blank	04	10%
4	Poor Administration	04	10%
5	No difficulties	06	15%
	Total	40	100%

Table No.5 shows that 25% students opinion is un availability of infrastructure is difficult to using ICT as resources, 15% students says that Absence of Experts difficult to using ICT, 10% students not answer this question, 10% students says that poor Administration is difficult to use ICT as Resources for doing Action Research and 15% students says that there is no difficulties to using ICT as resources for conducting action research.

Major findings of Research:-

- Majority of D.T.Ed. students know the concept of ICT very well.
- Many D.T.Ed. students are not using ICT for their action research.
- D.T.Ed. students not using internet for research review.

- Research shows that unavailability of infrastructure is major problem in D.T.Ed.colleges.

Recommendation For D.T.Ed.colleges:-

- D.T.Ed.colleges make show that they providing Quality education of ICT to second year students.
- College should provide good resources and infrastructure of ICT to D.T.Ed.second year students .
- D.T.Ed.colleges appoint well qualified teachers who interested and passionate to teach ICT subject.
- D.T.Ed.colleges make available updated computers,computer lab.with internet facility and also encourage students to use it.

Recommendation For Teachers:-

- ICT teachers in D.T.Ed.colleges encourage students to use ICT for various purpose in day to day life and study also.
- Teachers who teach Action Research subjects in D.T.Ed.colleges tell importance of computer in calculate data.
- While teachers teach action research they demonstrate students how to use internet getting review and other purpose.

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